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Staff Remuneration And Teamwork As Predictors Of Teachers' Job Performance In Public Secondary Schools In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined staff remuneration and teamwork as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Five research questions guided the study and five null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study is 267 principals in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. There was no sampling because the population was small and manageable by the researcher. Two instruments were used for data collection: Staff Remuneration Questionnaire (STRQ), Teamwork Questionnaire (TEWQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJP). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The instruments were further subjected to internal consistency reliability using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficient values of 0.83 for STRQ, 0.82 for TEWQ and 0.86 for TJPQ were obtained and considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that basic salary, promotion, fringe benefit, positively and significantly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study therefore concluded that staff remuneration positively and significantly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Keywords: Staff Remuneration, Basic Salary, Promotion, Fringe Benefit, Teachers' Teamwork, Shared Responsibility, Collegiality, Teachers' Job Performance

INTRODUCTION

Teachers promote quality education from the domain of teaching and learning through creative ideas, participation and cooperative learning, research, analysis and critical thinking, problem solving, innovation and encouragement of creative and divergent thinking. Teachers' activities in area of teaching and learning lead to proper development of knowledge, skills, attitudes, values that enable students to function effectively and live as responsible citizens and also make useful contribution to the society. Therefore, teachers' job performance play a crucial role in the students' learning processes. Good performance of students depends on the effective job performance of their teachers. In the same vein, Kaegon and Okere (2023) noted that teachers are expected to render a very high job performance and the ministry of education is always curious regarding the job performance of its teachers.

In the school system, teachers' job performance could be described as the duties performed by a teacher at any given time in school geared towards achieving both the daily school and classroom

objectives and the entire set goals and objectives of education. Such duties include among others: covering of scheme of work adequately, give and marking of continuous assessment regularly, be able to manage stubborn students in the class without distorting teaching and learning, preparing plan of any lesson to be taught among others. From the definitions one would understand that teachers' job performance is sine-qua-non for the achievement of educational goal at large.

Teachers' job performance referred to an act of accomplishing or executing a given task. It is defined as duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. Kaegon and Okere (2023) averred that teachers' job performance is the extent to which teachers can carry out the tasks successfully using school resources under regular conditions. When an individual is satisfied, their job performance might increase and tend to be more committed to their work. Job performance is important to ensure the quality of instruction taking place at schools. In schools, teachers' job performance can be mapped well through arranging training programmes for them and they will get motivated and their confidence also increases. Quines and Nino (2023) were of the opinion that social and economic conditions of teachers have an effect on teachers' job performance, that is, lack of facilities, status of teachers in society, teachers' mental health and moral, stress of work, relationship with the principals, working environment are all those factors that have strong impact on teachers job performance.

Staff remuneration is considered as a very important variable in increasing teachers' job performance. Remuneration is a part of reward received by employees as a result of their task in the organization, including gifts, awards or promotions. Performance cannot be achieved optimally if remuneration is not given proportionally. In addition, the individuals' attachment to work is the key to the success and profitability of the organization. Quines and Nino (2023) defined staff remuneration as monetary or non-monetary package in form of salaries, wages, bonuses, incentives, allowances and benefits that is accrued or given to an employee or group of employees by the employer as a result of services rendered by the employee(s) or commitment to the organization. Teachers' remuneration provides basic attraction to a teacher to perform their job efficiently and effectively. Nwankwo and Ifeanyi (2022) submitted that remuneration is the reward or compensation given to the teachers for their work performances. Remuneration leads to teachers' motivation. It constitutes an important source of income for teachers and determines their standard of living.

Teachers' basic salary is a fixed amount of money agreed every year as pay for employees, usually paid directly into their bank account every month. Salary is the regular payment by an employer to an employee for employment that is expressed either monthly or annually, but is paid most commonly on a monthly basis, especially to white collar workers, managers, directors and professionals (Obiora, 2019). Salary is a fixed amount of money or compensation paid to an employee by an employer in return for work performed. Salary is commonly paid in fixed intervals, for example, monthly payments of one-twelfth of the annual salary. It is typically determined by comparing market pay rates for people performing similar work in similar industries in the same region, and is also determined by leveling the pay rates and ranges established by an individual employer.

Teachers' promotion means the ascension of a teacher to higher ranks. It involves an increase in salary, position, responsibilities, status, and benefits. This aspect of the job drives teachers the most-the ultimate reward for dedication and loyalty towards the school. Aji (2021) opined that teachers' promotion is an upward mobility of teachers which changes their present position to one that makes them assume greater responsibility. Apart from bringing them more money, promotion has a higher motivating effect and it serves as a mark of recognition of teachers' performance. Hence, promotion can be seen as a feedback that the teachers have performed well. Promotion is the elevation to a higher job accompanied by increased pay and privileges (Onuorah & Nwene, 2019). It is an upward advancement of an employee in an organization, which commands better pay, better status, higher opportunities, higher responsibilities and better work environment.

Teachers' fringe benefits are additional compensation provided to teachers that is not directly related with their salary or wages for the performance of a specific service. Sunoma *et al.* (2022) noted that fringe benefits can make or break an organization's efforts to attract, recruit, and retain high-quality employees. Fringe benefits can come in many different forms and be tailored towards individuals or teams. For example, some benefits may be offered to compensate for work costs, while others may be rewarded based on performance. Some fringe benefits are required by law, while others are

voluntarily provided by the employer. Examples of fringe benefits include transportation benefits, retirement planning services, childcare, and education assistance, among others. Zulkiflee *et al.* (2023) noted that fringe benefits are a form of pay, often from employers to employees, and considered compensation for services beyond the employees' normal rate of pay. They can be made in the form of property, services, cash, or cash equivalents. Teachers' fringe benefits varies according to schools and can come in different forms like use of school bus, housing allowance, educational assistance and sick pay among others. Teachers' fringe benefits can also motivate them to work in teams and help to achieve school target goals.

Teamwork is the collaborative effort of a group to achieve a common goal or to complete a task in the most effective and efficient way. This concept is seen within the greater framework of a team, which is a group of interdependent individuals who work together towards a common goal. The four key characteristics of a team include a shared goal, interdependence, boundedness and stability, the ability to manage their own work and internal process, and operate in a bigger social system (Quines & Nino, 2023). Teamwork is seen as one of the key aspects of teachers' professional development and a vehicle to enhancing teachers' performance. The qualities and characteristics that fall under the labels of teachers' individualism, isolation, and privatism are widely perceived as threats or barriers to teachers' professional growth and development. Schools in recent years are believed to be the best place for teachers to learn and grow professionally. Schools are expected to begin to restructure in ways that can provide more opportunities for teachers to learn together.

Shared Responsibility is sometimes used with the concept of cooperation. This is because teams are formed to enhance the workforce and make all individuals or groups work together for the achievement of organisational goals and objectives. Building a team is vital in any formal organisation like the school, as it helps to improve the performance of all team members in the school system (Ihueze & Unachukwu, 2020). The importance of shared responsibility is exemplified when problems or challenges arise. Instead of one person grappling with an issue, a team that embraces shared responsibility collectively tackles the problem. Different perspectives and skills come together to find effective solutions. When responsibilities are shared, team members have the opportunity to develop new skills and expand their knowledge base. This helps in individual growth and career advancement, as team members become more versatile and capable of taking on diverse tasks.

For collegiality to thrive, the school environment and instructional climate would be conducive for principal, teachers and students to express a shared vision that will enable every member of the school community to succeed. Teachers and students will not be afraid to bring up their personal problems because they know that others are all one and feel the sense of belongingness. Principals and teachers including students are sure that their colleagues can offer excellent ideas that will help solve their problems. Member of the school community found here feel so free to learn from others who are better in what they do. Teaching and learning is a team sport and team play ought to be displayed. Principals can work as a team to evaluate and modify the curriculum, improvise for instructional materials, handle teachers and students' discipline without any feeling of threat. Esiaba (2023) however, defined collegiality as individuals' involvement with their peers on any level, be it intellectual, moral, political, social, and/or emotional. Esiaba further noted that collegiality encompasses professional and social/emotional interaction in the workplace.

Statement of the Problem

Over the past few years, public secondary schools in Anambra State has witnessed obvious loss of teachers' commitment to their professional responsibilities evidenced by poor attitude to duty and low performance of teachers in schools. More so, in some public secondary schools in Anambra State, teachers are said to be truant. Some come late to school, some teachers undertake irregular and unauthorized movement from school, some use the official hours for their private businesses, some do not exhibit zeal in performing assigned responsibilities, while some show low level of commitment to school activities. Due to this, many schools seem not to be living up to the expected standard of quality output despite the presence or availability of professionally trained teachers and facilities. At times, disloyalties, conspiracy, quarrels, among others, exist in public secondary schools between teachers, and between teachers and principals. Thus, the researcher sought to find out how staff remuneration and teamwork predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine staff remuneration and teamwork as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. basic salary predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. shared responsibility predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does basic salary predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. How does shared responsibility predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

3. Basic salary does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. Shared responsibility does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was a correlational research design. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. Anambra State is one of the five States in South-East Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria. The population of the study was 267 principals in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State (Planning, Research and Statistics Department, Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC), Awka Anambra State as at Second Term 2023-2024 Academic Session). There is no sampling because the population was small and manageable by the researcher. The entire population of 267 principals was used for the study. Sheskin (2020) noted that the entire population can be studied when it is small and manageable by the researcher. The sampling of the study was 267 and was manageable by the researcher. The entire population of 267 principals was used for the study. Three instruments were used for data collection: Staff Remuneration Questionnaire (STRQ), Teamwork Questionnaire (TEWQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJP). The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. On the other hand, construct validation was carried out with the help SPSS v.25. The construct validity of the instrument for the staff remuneration, teamwork and teachers' job performance components loading six factors was explored using Principal Component Analysis approach. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) as a measure of sampling adequacy to conduct the Principal Component Analysis. The data obtained were subjected to test for internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha which yielded co-efficient values of 0.84 for basic salary; 0.85 for promotion; 0.83 for fringe benefits; 0.83 for shared responsibility; 0.81 for collegiality; and 0.86 for teachers' job performance were obtained. The average coefficient values of 0.84 for STRQ, 0.82 for TEWQ and 0.86 for TJPQ. The instruments were administered by the researcher with the help of three research assistants using direct approach whereby the researcher and assistants waited for the respondents to complete the questionnaire immediately and retrieve them back. A period of five weeks was used for the administration and retrieval of the instruments. Simple regression analysis was used to analyze the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. This statistical tool was used because this was a relationship study that tends to measure the extent of association between quantitative independent variables and quantitative dependent variables.

For Regression Coefficient (r)

+ Sign = Positive Prediction

- Sign = Negative Prediction

The negative sign means a negative coefficient which indicates a negative prediction or correlation between variables, while a positive sign means a positive coefficient which indicates a positive prediction or correlation between variables.

For Sig. (2-tailed) when

Sig. (2-tailed) < .05: Reject H_0 and Accept H_1

Sig. (2-tailed) > .05: Do not reject H_0

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was accepted.

Research Question 1: *How does basic salary predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with basic salary as predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	27.471	7.105	
Basic Salary	.592	.397	.584
R	.584		
R ²	.492		
Adj. R ²	.477		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that basic salary positively predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.584$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.492 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 49% of the variations in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' basic salary. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.477 indicating that 48% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job performance) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' basic salary). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of basic salary is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.584$) showed that teachers' basic salary is a positive predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit change in teachers' basic salary led to 0.584(58%) increase in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Hence, the positive prediction of teachers' basic salary on their job performance means that teachers' job performance moderately depends on the adequate and prompt payment of teachers' basic salary in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: *How does shared responsibility predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with shared responsibility as predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	31.541	6.493	
Shared Responsibility	.664	.257	.627
R	.627		
R ²	.565		
Adj. R ²	.529		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that shared responsibility positively predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra

State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.627$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.565 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 57% of the variations in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' shared responsibility. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.528 indicating that 53% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job performance) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' shared responsibility). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of shared responsibility is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.627$) showed that teachers' shared responsibility is a positive predictor of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in teachers' shared responsibility led to 0.627(63%) increase in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' shared responsibility on their job performance means that teachers' job performance moderately depends on the practices of teachers' sharing responsibilities styles in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Basic salary does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with basic salary does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	27.471	7.105		22.975	.000
Basic Salary	.592	.397	.584	20.124	.000
R	.584				
R^2	.492				
Adj. R^2	.477				
F	30.427				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.584 while the R^2 is 0.492 and Adjust R^2 is 0.477. The F-ratio associated with regression is 30.427, the t-test is 20.124 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that basic salary does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that basic salary significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₄: Shared responsibility does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with shared responsibility does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	31.541	6.493		28.182	.000
Shared Responsibility	.664	.257	.627	21.451	.000
R	.627				
R^2	.565				
Adj. R^2	.529				
F	34.286				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.627 while the R^2 is 0.565 and Adjust R^2 is 0.529. The F-ratio

associated with regression is 34.186, the t-test is 21.451 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that shared responsibility does not significantly predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that shared responsibility significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION

Findings on how basic salary predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that basic salary positively and significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Salary occupies a strategic position among the different reward packages that school administrators use to manage the performance of their employees. In line with the findings, Obiora (2019) believed that salary has a great influence on employee activities. . It was also indicated from the study that salary contributes to teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State by 49% as indicated by the coefficient of determination. This implies that payment of teachers' basic salary has a moderate level of prediction on the performance of teachers. Grub (2020) agreed otherwise that salary earned does not affect the attitude to work of any employee.

Findings on how shared responsibility predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that shared responsibility positively and significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the findings of Ayeni and Fakunle (2022) which showed that there was a positive and significant level to which teachers perceive the use of shared responsibility styles in secondary schools. The shared responsibility among teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State were to constitute different committee to foster teamwork among teachers, assign group responsibility to some teachers, encourage team teaching among teachers, entrust the responsibility of organizing sporting activities to group of teachers to work as a team and team up with teachers to develop school programmes. Shared responsibilities are possibly adopted in schools to encourage diverse perspectives to solving problems and improve the job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the outcome of this study, it becomes evident that staff remuneration is an important force for improving teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Staff remuneration is extremely important in public secondary schools due to the fact that performance of secondary education relates directly to the quality of prevailing staff remuneration programmes available and teachers' teamwork in schools. The study therefore concluded that staff remuneration positively and significantly predicted teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The government through school management board in Anambra State can cultivate the practice of empowering teachers by giving them well-paid packages and proper remuneration like leave allowance, basic salary, promotion, fringe benefits and other allowances to encourage teachers to function efficiently.
2. School principals on a regular basis should recommend to the school management board the teachers that are qualified and due for promotion as at when due. This will encourage teachers to put in their best in their job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

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